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**The Impact of Social Media on the Parliamentary Performance of
the Members of the Jordanian 18th Parliament
from their Perspectives
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Abstract:

The study aims at exploring the degree of parliament's follow-up to social media; to identify the degree of social media coverage of the topics needed by the MPs (Members of Parliament) in the Parliament of Jordan; to explain the degree of the impact of social media on the legislative and regulatory role of the MPs; and to measure the degree of the impact of social media on the interaction and communication of MPs with citizens. The study was carried out on the methodology of quantitative descriptive analysis. A questionnaire was developed as a major tool for collecting data. The researcher adopted the cluster (purposeful) sample consisting of (75) MPs who constitute (58%) of The total size of the study population. A statistical analysis program (SPSS) was used to analyze and process data. The study concluded that the topics needed by MPs in the Jordanian Parliament are covered highly by social media; the impact of social media on the legislative and oversight role of the MPs scored a moderate degree; and that the impact of social media toward the interaction and communication of MPs with citizens scored a high degree. In the light of the study's results, it is recommended holding training workshops for members of the House of Representatives about how to deal with social media and electronic media, and to improve the communication and interaction with citizens.

Keywords:

The Eighteenth Jordanian Parliament, Parliamentary Performance, Legislative Role, Oversight Role, Social Media

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Introduction:

Pace of change in the world accelerates continuously since the development of technology, such as the development of mobile phone, played a vital role in shaping the impact of social media all over the world dominated by mobile devices regarding total minutes spent by one online. So, social media is found whenever and wherever on any device with everyone. Different ways and means of social media are considered one of the most significant constituents of the world today respecting all its cultural, intellectual and ideological facts. Importance of media emerges through the various issues suggested which can influence the recipient and give rise to radical changes in its ideas and beliefs particularly at the present time which witnesses the domination of technological means on all facts of human life. Everyone, whatever their orientation or address was, became able to communicate limitlessly and boundlessly with others within a few seconds, the media process is done via media. The culture advances through the ideology of society. Ideology of the society is a changeable concept, i.e. it is defined according to the cultural and intellectual approaches and cultural and political attitudes in society.

In political systems the parliament, with its two main functions: the function of legislation and that of control over works of the executive power, is entrusted with the legislative power. Due to the extension of works of the executive power, the ministry, and getting involved in many domains and extensive activities with exceptional privileges and powers enabling it to practice these activities, the need to activate the role of parliamentary work emerges for keeping pace with developments of the executive work so that principle of balance between executive and legislative power can be achieved and no power can infringe on the other or deviate from the right path. Parliament controls over the executive power works in many ways included in most constitutions, including the Constitution of the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, laws and internal regulations leading to parliamentary oversight practicing political effects make the ministry or one of the ministers being held accountable for any public affairs to be entrusted with the ministry or the minister and resulting in censuring confidence in the ministry or the minister. (Al-Mashaqba 2012).

Since social media networks have been launched on the internet, these websites pioneers reach millions of its users on Facebook, twitter, WhatsApp and the like.

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These networks are still spreading widely because it is considered a revolution in the field of communications and its considerable potentials. In Jordan an influential role of social media networks in having effect on the government decisions has emerged. In addition, it played an important role in leadership of public opinion and effectiveness of popular control, affecting taking or annulling decisions, making governments held accountable and controlling the performance of Parliamentary assemblies because social media networks granted the citizen a chance to practice the direct, rapid and pressing control over governments and parliamentary assemblies which directly have impact on decisions, governmental performance and parliamentary performance of MPs (Members of Parliament). Hence, social media became a supervisor of the general performance on the whole and the parliamentary performance of MPs (Members of Parliament). Therefore, the present study was done in order to tackle the role of social media networks in impacting the parliamentary performance from the perspective of the Members of the eighteenth Parliament to clarify the degree of the impact of social media networks on the legislative and regulatory role of the MP and measure the degree of the impact of social media networks on the interaction and communication of MPs with citizens.

The Research Problem:

In the light of accelerated technological and scientific development and manifestations of globalization in various walks of economic and cultural life, interest in the performance of parliamentary assemblies has been increased. It became the focus of interest to the peoples as it expresses their will and aspirations by enacting the laws which consider their interests and maintain their rights which intensifies the role of parliamentary assemblies in peoples' life. It is no longer the legislative power which stands against the executive power and limits its infringement on individuals but it also faces, in addition to the executive power, the globalization consequences which is too accelerating to expect its results. Whoever follow up the parliamentary performance of parliaments in general will notice that social media has an impact on the parliamentary performance because it affected and controlled the performance of MPs (Members of Parliament) and represented the pressing public opinion towards their performance and stances in parliament. Abdelaziz (2012) denoted the pivotal role of social media in exchanging ideas and experiences between individuals as open-ended dialogs can destabilize a country as a whole. So, the researcher believes in the necessity of fact-finding the impact of social media on the performance, stances and actions of MPs (Members of Parliament) and the role of these websites in upgrading their performance and enhancing their interaction with citizens. The research question can be crystallized in answering the following question: to what extent social media networks affected the parliamentary performance from the perspective of Members of the eighteenth Parliament?

Significance of the study:

Significance of this study lies in the results and analyses presented by it to researchers and students in the field of the legislative and regulatory role of the parliament to make use of it as later studies and from which Members of Jordanian Parliament can benefit for the purpose of developing their performance. The impact of these websites on the Jordanian people has grown the fact which affected and played a vital role in transitions made in political arena. Also, it played an important role in shaping attitudes and opinions, shaping and directing the public opinion, and presenting the internal and external political issues. These websites emerged as an impact and pressure on the parliamentary and government performance. Hence, we find that social media networks had an impact on the parliamentary performance of MPs which affected the legislative role of the MP concerning dealing with legislations and laws. Also, social media affected the regulatory role of the MP in controlling governments and presenting the parliamentary questions. The MP senses the societal oversight over his performance intuiting the significance of control of social media over him. Also, concerning the communication of MPs (Members of Parliament) on social media and interaction with citizens and their issues, the significance of interaction of MPs on social media is crystal clear in order to achieve the continuous communication with citizens.

Research aims:

The study aims at:

- Clarifying to what extent MPs follow up the social media and cover the topics needed by the MP (Member of Parliament) in Parliament of Jordan?
- Clarifying to what extent social media has an impact on the legislative and regulatory role of the Member of Parliament?
- Measuring to what extent social media has an impact on interaction and communication of MPs with citizens?
- Measuring the statistically significant differences of MPs attitudes towards the impact of social media on the parliamentary performance from the perspective of Members of the eighteenth Parliament according to the difference of qualification.

Research questions:

The study aims at answering the following questions:

First question: To what extent MPs follow the social media and how it cover issues needed by MP in Parliament of Jordan?

Second question: Is there any impact of the social media on the legislative and regulatory role of the Member of Parliament?

Third question: Is there any impact of social media on interaction and communication of MPs with citizens?

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Fourth question: are there any statistically significant differences of MPs attitudes towards the impact of social media on the parliamentary performance from the perspective of Members of the eighteenth Parliament according to the difference of qualification?

Hypotheses:

The study tackles the following hypothesis: there is no statistically significant impact on the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of social media on the parliamentary performance from the perspective of Members of the eighteenth Parliament according to the difference of qualification.

Research limits and limitations:

The study is limited to the period of time from 2019-2020 in Amman, Jordan as the study is applied to the Members of the Jordanian 18th Parliament, whereas the study is limited to the descriptive quantitative methodology as it used the questionnaire as a research instrument for the purpose of gathering information.

Concepts and terms of the study:

Social media: a set of electronic networks let the user create their own websites and hence connect him through an electronic social system with the other group members with the same interests and hobbies (**Radhi, 2013**).

Parliament of Jordan: a Jordanian national assembly. Established by the 1964 Constitution. It represents the legislative power in the country. The legislature consists of two houses: the Senate and the House of Representatives. The Senate has 65 members, all of whom are directly appointed by the King, while the House of Representatives has 130 members elected by the people, with nine seats reserved for Christians, three are for Circassian and Chechen minorities, and fifteen for women (quota, membership of both houses serve for four-year terms.) Parliament of Jordan is also called the Jordanian Parliament. This assembly is also accountable for number of legislative powers and consists of two houses; the Senate and the House of Representatives, the members of the former are appointed by the King while the members of the latter are elected by the people. The king is the one held responsible for appointing the members of the Senate. The Speaker of the Senate has a term of two years which can be renewed for the next term. A member of the Senate has a term of four years which can also be renewable in case of being ended. (Addabbas, 2008.)

Parliament: a term coined in the thirteenth century referring to a discussion meeting, it is originally a French word derived from the verb (Parler). It is the legislative body of government which declares the laws and oversees the executive power (Kayali, 1990.)

The eighteenth Parliament: the assembly elected on 20/9/2016 pursuant to Elections Law in 2016 when number of seats in the Parliament went down from 150 to 130 member. The Parliament is a legislative body represents the legislative power in the constitutional countries. Pursuant to article No. 67 of the Jordanian Constitution, the Parliament of Jordan consists of publicly, secretly and directly elected members according to Elections Law. (Al-Mashaqba, 2017).

Parliamentary oversight refers to the parliamentary oversight of the executive power as to the performance of the powers granted by the Constitution. In democratic systems Parliaments are entitled to oversee the executive power because these assemblies represent the people's will and express their aspirations. Undoubtedly declaring the right of Parliament to oversee the works of the executive power is a means to improve the performance of the Parliament by regarding the public interest. Question, desire or decision proposal, constituting investigative committees, questionnaire and censuring, a public issue for discussion are the tools used for parliamentary oversight. (Addabbas, 2008.)

Legislative role: the main role held by the Parliament, its function is limited to making, amending and revoking laws regulating the state affairs and individuals' life. Parliament should originally be apart from any restrictions limits its power to practice legislation but considerations of the actual practice may necessitate the interference of both judicial and executive powers in the Parliamentary actions in various degrees which differ from a system to another. The parliament, when practicing legislation, abides by traditions, values and concepts prevailing in the society (Al-Odwan, 2004).

Theoretical framework:

Social media started to prevail in early 2007 and widely and effectively spread between people through sign up for these websites to communicate with individuals who are interested in their specializations, so they communicate, discuss and chat. When public figures pay attention to this, they create their own accounts to communicate with their own public and interact with them in everything matter to them. Then they watch the interaction towards what they say, and see any emerging questions, remarks, criticism, and reservations. Social media is known to be "online websites provide their users with a chance for dialog, and exchange information, opinions, ideas and problems through profiles, photo albums, chat rooms and so on" these websites are like Twitter, Facebook, YouTube and MySpace (Al-Mansour). In Jordan global statistics refer to the passion of Jordanians and their extensive use of different social media networks (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Snapchat etc.) A world study by Pew Research Center has classified Jordan in the first rank worldwide in the index of percentage of number of social media websites and platforms users to internet

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users. According to the last statistics of Telecommunications Regulatory Commission in 2018, number of internet subscriptions in Jordan has reached 9.1 million (Telecommunications Regulatory Commission 2019.) There are some reasons behind the extensive use of social media by Jordanians: the growth in social media use generally in Jordan, availability of broadband networks particularly the 3G and 4G broadband mobile internet, the growing use of smart phones though being cheap besides the big awareness and passion of use of different types of social media networks in daily life, for work purposes, marketing, promotion and media. (Al-Imbaydeen 2016.)

Social media is used in a way which shapes policy, works, world culture, education and other domains. Over the last years an impact of social media on the public speech and communication with community has been noticed. Social media is increasingly used in the political context lately in particular. It is said that small blogs services (such as Twitter) and social media websites (such as Facebook) are able to increase the political participation. Twitter is an ideal platform for users to post not only information in general but political views through their networks as well. So, political organizations (such as politicians, political parties and political organizations and so on) started to use Facebook pages or groups to chat with citizens and encourage more political discussions. Literature review has shown that from the perspective of political organizations an emerging need to collect, observe, analyze, summarize, and visualize relevant political information from social media. These activities, classified as "social media analyses", are difficult tasks due to numerous different social media platforms in addition to the considerable amount of information and data and its complexity. Methods of tracking and methodological analysis besides suitable scientific techniques and styles in the political are not present yet. (Stieglitz & Dang-Xuan, 2013).

Media is not limited to the traditional media and information monopoly. Different social media networks became arena of electoral battles targeting the votes. Also, social media participated in paving the way for individuals and groups to express their political views through which many activities relevant to public affair have been practiced such as expressing the different political stances and so on. It cannot replace the traditional media but is parallel to it in order to exceed and break the traditional rules in one-sided unilateralism provided by the traditional media but move to the interaction in dialog and raising issues. (Qutbi, 2018).

Social media has an impact on the growth of transparency in parliamentary work. Shaneikat (2018) stated that it is important to find a political and legislative environment to enhance the parliamentary transparency principle particularly concerning the job of parliamentary committees which must be

available to all and to find mechanisms entrusting MPs with compliance with the internal system of Parliament through activating penalties in case of breach and not complying with attendance in particular and mechanisms of using the regulatory tools. Additionally, the study urges that MPs must only perform the regulatory and legislative functions and not exploit their Parliamentary position for personal interests.

The world witnesses number of developments which directly affected the regulatory role of Parliaments including Arab Parliaments. The most distinguished developments lie in two main and important variables; the first variable is a political one lying in the spread of Parliamentary democratic systems, the second variable brought by the tremendous technological revolution which invaded means of communication and transportation the fact that led to the easy flow of information and easy communication with individuals including communication between the citizen and the official, the citizen and the MP, citizens in different countries, and MPs in different countries besides the wide awareness acquired by the citizen in a country around the parliamentary experiences worldwide. (Assmadi, 2017).

Method and procedures

This chapter handles a description of the study sample and community, how to choose the sample, tools used for collecting information, procedures to build and develop it, necessary steps to ensure the credibility and stability of tools, applied procedures, and statistical processes used for processing study data.

Research method and ways to collect and analyze information:

The study was carried out on the methodology of quantitative descriptive analysis. A questionnaire was developed as a major tool for collecting data from the study sample, and the phenomenon or problem has been studied through describing scientifically and then having access to logical interpretations with evidences and proofs so that the researcher can define the problem. This method helps state how social media websites have impact on the performance of Members of the eighteenth Parliament.

Research community:

It consists of all Members of the eighteenth Parliament (130 member).

Research sample:

The researcher adopted the cluster (purposeful) sample consisting of (75) MPs who constitute (58%) of the total size of the study including Members of the eighteenth Parliament.

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The characteristics of the study sample are as follows:

Research tools

To achieve the study targets the researcher resorts to the use of two main sources for collecting information:

Secondary sources: books, journals, researches, internet to revise the relevant literature review for collecting these information to build the theoretical framework of this study to serve the purposes of the study and designs of questionnaire.

Preliminary sources: preliminary data has been collected through the questionnaire which the researcher developed as a major tool of the study that included number of paragraphs reflecting the research aims and questions answered by the respondents and questionnaire has been designed in its final image relying on the relevant literature review including the study of (Shaneikat, 2018), (Assaaideh, 2015), and (Aru'd 2012). Questionnaire contained information on the follow-up of social media networks which consists of four questions. Questionnaire covered four dimensions; first dimension: coverage of social media websites of topics needed by Member of Parliament in the Parliament of Jordan which consists of (6) paragraphs, second dimension: impact of social media on the legislative role of the Parliament which consists of (7) paragraphs, third dimension: impact of social media on the regulatory role of the Parliament which consists of (12) paragraphs, fourth dimension: impact of social media on interaction and communication of MPs with citizens which consists of (6) paragraphs.

Research procedures:

- 1- The researcher depended on the literature review and number of relevant studies and then designed a questionnaire consisting of three parts: the first part contained general information about the individuals of the study sample, second part contained information about the follow-up of social media, and third part contained questionnaire paragraphs.
- 2- The researcher made sure of the credibility of research tool by being viewed by number of arbitrators and making amends based on the arbitrators' remarks.
- 3- The researcher made sure of the stability of research tool by applying Cronbach's alpha to know the internal consistency stability coefficient of the original sample.
- 4- After the researcher made sure of the convenience and validity of the research tool, he defined the study population and then defined the study sample and (75) forms have been collected.
- 5- Then the researcher entered data by statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) to analyze and then reach and discuss results, and give recommendations in this respect.

Stability using Cronbach's alpha

To ensure the stability of internal consistency of study variables, Cronbach's alpha has been applied. Stability coefficient of the study tool through Cronbach's alpha has reached (0.928), it is a high stability coefficient suiting the study purposes. Also, stability coefficients of every dimension have been computed as results show that stability coefficients of study variables suiting its purposes.

Processing and statistical styles used:

Statistical analysis program (SPSS) has been used for analyzing and processing data, so Cronbach's alpha is used for making sure of the stability of search tool by computing the internal consistency of the study tool. Arithmetic means and standard deviations are used for showing the study results. To answer the question of difference test, t-test of paired samples and one-way analysis of variance have been applied.

Viewing the field study results

This chapter shows the results of the study through data analysis and statistical analysis results. The results are as follows:

First question: what is the degree of parliament's follow-up to social media and the degree of social media coverage of the topics needed by the MPs (Members of Parliament) in the Parliament of Jordan?

First: the degree of parliament's follow-up to social media:

Table (1)

The proportional distribution of the study sample individuals according to the degree of parliament's follow-up to social media (N=75)

Variable	Number	Percentage	
Widely used social media websites	Facebook	45	60.0
	Twitter	7	9.3
	WhatsApp	23	30.7
the degree of follow-up to social media	Daily	59	78.7
	Weekly	16	21.3
The duration of following up the account on social media websites	Less than an hour daily	19	25.3
	From 2 to 3 hours daily	37	49.3
	From 4 to 5 hours daily	12	16.0
	6 hours and more	7	9.3
The role of social media websites to increase the ability to follow events and news in Jordan	Yes	64	85.3
	No	11	14.7

According to table (1) details, it is clear that social media website, Facebook, is widely used by MPs with the percentage of 60.0%, then WhatsApp with the percentage of 30.7% but Twitter is the rarely used with the percentage of 9.3%.

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Concerning the follow-up of social media websites the results indicate that they are followed daily by most MPs (78.7%) and weekly (21.3%). Additionally, table details denote that the time spent by MPs to follow-up social media websites is long in general as 49.3% spend 2-3 hours daily and 16.0% spend 4-5 hours daily to follow-up. Concerning the impact of social media websites on the increase of ability to follow-up events and news in Jordan, results show that the majority (85.3%) stated that it has a role, however, 14.7% do not believe that social media websites have a role in increasing the ability to follow-up events and news in Jordan.

Second: the degree of social media coverage of the topics needed by the MPs (Members of Parliament) in the Parliament of Jordan:

Table (2)

Arithmetic means and deviations of the degree of social media coverage of the topics needed by the MPs (Members of Parliament) in the Parliament of Jordan

Paragraph No.	Paragraph	Grade	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Mark
1	Using social media websites to follow-up event and political issues in Jordan	2	4.13	0.88	High
2	Using social media websites to view the latest Arab and world news for me	1	4.24	0.91	High
3	I depend on social media websites to obtain all political information	5	3.21	1.26	Medium
4	The social media websites post the political events around the clock	3	4.03	0.82	High
5	I can obtain the information I want at any time through social media websites	4	3.79	0.62	High
6	Social media websites is considered the main source of political news and events for me.	6	3.12	0.73	Medium
	Total mark	---	3.75	0.66	High

According to the table (2) it is clear that topics needed by the MP in the Parliament of Jordan are highly covered as the total arithmetic mean reached (3.75) with a standard deviation of (0.66). On the level of scale paragraphs, it is

clear that the paragraph No. (2) obtained the highest degree of approval which states that "Using social media websites to view the latest Arab and world news for me" with arithmetic mean of (4.24) and standard deviation of (0.91), while the paragraph No. (6) stating that "Social media websites is considered the main source of political news and events for me" came in the last grade with an arithmetic mean of (3.12) and standard deviation of (0.73).

Second question: is there any impact of social media websites on the regulatory and legislative role of the MP (Member of Parliament)?

First: impact of social media websites on the legislative role of the MP (Member of Parliament):

Table (3)

Arithmetic means and standard deviations on paragraphs of the impact of social media websites on the legislative role of the MP (Member of Parliament)

Paragra ph No.	Paragraph	Grade	Arithme tic mean	Standard deviation	Mark
1	I depend on social media websites as it provides me with information about the draft laws tackled by the Parliament	6	3.24	0.91	Medium
2	Social media websites provide me with feedback information about the legislations needed by the Jordanian society.	3	3.88	0.57	High
3	Information of social media websites give me the ability to determine the importance and priorities of laws to be handled	2	3.89	0.73	High
4	Social media websites help me to know the concerned parties impacted by the suggested laws.	4	3.79	0.78	High
5	Social media websites help the Parliament receives suggestions of draft laws by the parties and civil society organizations.	7	3.15	0.88	High
6	Social media websites participated in enhancing my ability in the legislative field.	5	3.44	0.68	Medium
7	Though social media websites one can able to define the reactions of the Jordanian street around the projects declared by the Parliament.	1	4.33	0.47	High
	Total mark	---	3.67	0.52	Medium

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According to the table (3) it is clear that impact of social media websites on the legislative role of the MP (Member of Parliament) obtained a medium mark as the total arithmetic mean reached (3.67) with a standard deviation of (0.55). On the level of scale paragraphs it is remarkable that paragraph No. (7) obtained the highest mark of approval which states that "Though social media websites one can able to define the reactions of the Jordanian street around the projects declared by the Parliament." with an arithmetic mean of (4.33) and standard deviation of (0.47), while the paragraph No. (5) which states that "Social media websites help the Parliament receives suggestions of draft laws by the parties and civil society organizations" in the final degree with an arithmetic mean of (3.15) and standard deviation of (0.88).

Second: is there any impact of social media websites on the regulatory role of the MP (Member of Parliament):

Table (4)

Arithmetic means and standard deviations on the paragraphs of the impact of the social media on the regulatory role of the MP (Member of Parliament)

Paragraph No.	Paragraph	Grade	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Mark
1	Social media websites enhance my ability to follow-up the government performance	1	4.21	0.41	High
2	Social media websites enhance my ability to question the government about different issues.	3	4.00	0.81	High
3	Social media websites enhance my ability to follow-up the corruption files	4	3.99	0.67	High
4	Social media websites enhance my ability to coordinate with audit bureau and exchange information with it.	7	3.21	0.62	Medium
5	Social media websites help me identify the glitches in the various service sectors	2	4.09	0.57	High
6	Social media websites support the performance of the regulatory role of the Parliament on the government	5	3.88	0.33	High

7	Social media websites enhance confidence between the Parliament and community	12	2.41	1.16	Medium
8	Social media websites participates in enhancing separation of powers	11	2.97	1.16	Medium
9	Social media websites participates in enhancing the Jordanian justice	10	2.97	0.96	Medium
10	Social media websites support the performance of the regulatory role of the Parliament to support fiscal transparency principle	8	3.19	1.05	Medium
11	Social media websites support the performance of the regulatory role of the Parliament to participate in the democratic transition positively.	9	3.01	0.95	Medium
12	Social media websites participates in enabling the MP to evaluate himself and his performance	6	3.53	1.09	Medium
	Total mark	---	3.46	0.59	Medium

According to the table (4) it is clear that the impact of social media websites on the regulatory role of the MP (Member of Parliament) showed a medium degree as the total arithmetic mean reached (3.46) with a standard deviation of (0.59). On the level of scale paragraphs it is remarkable that paragraph No. (1) came in the highest degree of approval which states that "Social media websites enhance my ability to follow-up the government performance" with an arithmetic mean of (4.21) and standard deviation of (0.41), while the paragraph No. (7) which states that "Social media websites enhance confidence between the Parliament and community" in the final degree and with an arithmetic mean of (2.41) and standard deviation of (1.16).

Third question: is there any impact of social media websites on the interaction and communication of the MPs (Members of Parliament) with citizens?

Table (5)

Arithmetic means and standard deviations on the paragraphs of the impact of social media websites on the interaction and communication of the MPs (Members of Parliament) with citizens

Paragraph No.	Paragraph	Grade	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Mark
1	Social media websites enhance my ability to interact and communicate with citizens	1	4.43	0.50	High

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2	Social media websites participate in posting and sharing my stances with citizens on the legislative and regulatory level.	2	4.33	0.68	High
3	Social media websites enhance my ability to interact with local and international issues	3	4.20	0.64	Medium
4	Social media websites enhance my ability to answer questions of citizens regarding issues and legislations and to clarify what is unclear	5	4.04	0.88	High
5	Social media websites enhance my ability to share citizens and carry out poll in the important situations and decisions taken in the Parliament	4	4.16	0.68	High
6	Social media websites enhance my ability to determine problems, challenges and priorities faced by citizens.	6	3.99	0.94	High
	Total mark	---	4.24	0.52	High

According to table (5) it is clear that the impact of Social media websites on the interaction and communication of MPs (Members of Parliament) with citizens obtained the high degree as the total arithmetic mean reached (4.24) with a standard deviation of (0.52). On the level of scale paragraphs it is remarkable that the paragraph No.(1) reached the highest degree of approval which states that "Social media websites enhance my ability to interact and communicate with citizens" with an arithmetic mean of (4.43) and standard deviation of (0.50), while the paragraph No. (6) which states that "Social media websites enhance my ability to determine problems, challenges and priorities faced by citizens." Obtained the final grade with an arithmetic mean of (3.99) and standard deviation of (0.94).

Fourth question: are there any statistically significant differences of MPs attitudes towards the impact of social media on the parliamentary performance from the perspective of Members of the eighteenth Parliament according to the difference of qualification?

Table (6)

Scheffe' Test results to state the impact of social media websites on the regulatory role of the MP (Member of Parliament) and the impact of social media websites on interaction and communication of MPs (Members of Parliament) with citizens according to the qualification

Variable	Qualification (a)	Qualification (b)	Mean difference	Statistical significance
	Diploma or below	Bachelor	-0.417	0.409
		Master	0.000	1.000
		PhD	0.265	0.799
		Diploma or	0.417	0.409

Impact of social media websites on the regulatory role of MP (Member of Parliament)	Bachelor	below		
		Master	0.417	0.409
		PhD	0.681	*0.000
	Master	Diploma or below	0.000	1.000
		Bachelor	-0.417	0.409
		PhD	0.265	0.799
	PhD	Diploma or below	0.265	0.799
		Bachelor	-0.681	*0.000
		Master	-0.265	0.799
Impact of social media websites on the interaction and communication of MPs (Members of Parliament) with citizens	Diploma or below	Bachelor	-0.633	*0.011
		Master	0.000	1.000
		PhD	0.141	1.917
	Bachelor	Diploma or below	0.633	*0.011
		Master	0.633	*0.011
		PhD	0.755	*0.000
	Master	Diploma or below	0.000	1.000
		Bachelor	-0.633	*0.011
		PhD	0.141	1.917
	PhD	Diploma or below	-0.141	0.917
		Bachelor	-0.775	*0.000
		Master	-0.141	0.917

* statistically significant differences on the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

It is remarkable that Scheffe' Test results show statistically significant differences on the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the impact of social media websites on the regulatory role of the MP because of the difference of qualification between bachelor and PhD and for PhD. Also, statistically significant differences are detected on the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the impact of social media websites on interaction and communication of MPs (Members of Parliament) with citizens between diploma and below and bachelor, and for bachelor, also bachelor and all other levels (diploma, master, PhD) for (diploma, master, PhD).

Results:

The results concluded by the study are as follows:

First question: what is the degree of parliament's follow-up to social media and the degree of social media coverage of the topics needed by the MP (Member of Parliament) in the Parliament of Jordan?

First: the degree of parliament's follow-up to social media websites:

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It is clear that social media website (Facebook) is widely used by MPs (Members of Parliament) with the percentage of (60.0%) as the result has coincided with the study of (Addabisi and Chefs, 2013) which categorized Facebook in the first rank among networks with the percentage of 83%. In the recent study WhatsApp obtained the second grade with the use percentage of (30.7). However, Twitter was rarely used with a percentage of (9.3%). Concerning the degree of follow-up to social media websites results show that majority of MPs (78.7%) follows it up daily and (21.3) weekly. Additionally, the study results indicated that the time spent by MPs (Members of Parliament) to follow up social media websites is long on the whole as (49.3%) spend from 2-3 hours daily and (16.0%) from 4-5 hours daily to follow up. Moreover, the study concluded around the impact of social media websites on the increase of the ability to follow up events and news in Jordan results show that majority (85.3%) answered that it has a role while (14.7) do not believe that social media websites have a role in the increase of ability to follow up events and news in Jordan.

Second: the degree of social media coverage of the topics needed by the MP (Member of Parliament) in the Parliament of Jordan:

The study indicates that the topics needed by the MP in the Parliament of Jordan are highly covered by social media websites as the total arithmetic mean reached (3.75). This is clear via using social media websites for reading the Arab and world latest news to follow up the political issues and events in Jordan and have access to all the political information and events around the clock and have access to information required by the MP (Member of Parliament) whenever via social media websites which are the main source for political events and news. This coincides with a study conducted by Abd Arrazzaq and Al-Dulaimi (2013) which indicates that a high proportion of the study individuals became highly aware of the political events owing to using social media websites.

Second question: is there any impact of the social media on the legislative role of the Member of Parliament?

The study showed that the impact of the social media websites on the legislative role of the Member of Parliament got the medium degree as the total arithmetic mean reached (3.67) which is clarified through the ability of social media websites to identify the reactions of the Jordanian street around the projects declared by the Parliament of Jordan and that these websites provide MPs (Members of Parliament) with information to determine the importance and priorities of laws to be handled. Also, websites provide MPs (Members of Parliament) feedback (information) about the legislations to be needed by the Jordanian society. It also makes MPs (Members of Parliament) aware of the concerned parties who are affected by the given laws, and the Parliament receives suggestions of draft laws by the parties and civil society organizations. The MP depends on social media websites as it provides him with information

about draft laws tackled by the Parliament and through social media websites gets to know the reactions of the Jordanian street around the projects declared by the Parliament. Karakiza (2015) insisted that social media networks connected between the public and decision makers and that networks have effectiveness and rationality in taking decisions and different legislations.

Impact of social media websites on the regulatory role of the MP (Member of Parliament):

The analysis results show that the impact of social media websites on the regulatory role of the MP (Member of Parliament) reached a medium degree as the total arithmetic mean reached (3.46). This is clarified through the ability of social media websites to enhance the MP's ability to follow up the performance of government. Also, social media websites help the MP identify the glitches in the various service sectors, enhance the MP's ability to question the government about different issues, enhance the MP's ability to follow up the corruption issues, enhance the confidence between the Parliament and the society, perform the regulatory role of the Parliament in a way enhances the fiscal transparency principle, and positive democratic transition process. Social media websites support the performance of the regulatory role of the Parliament on the government and the ability to coordinate with audit bureau and exchange information with it, enable the MP (Member of Parliament) to evaluate oneself and one's performance, enhance separation of powers, and enhance the social justice. Aru'd study (2012) concluded that social media networks play a role in having an impact on the regulatory role and internal and external public opinion.

Third question: is there any impact of social media websites on the interaction and communication of MPs (Members of Parliament) with citizens?

The analysis results indicated that the impact of social media websites on the interaction and communication of MPs (Members of Parliament) with citizens obtained high degree as the total arithmetic mean reached (4.24) through the fact that social media websites enhance the MP's ability to interact and communicate with citizens, social media websites participate in posting and making citizens aware of the MP's stances at the legislative and regulatory level. Additionally, social media websites enhance the MP's ability to interact with local and international issues. Moreover, social media websites enhance the MP's ability to share citizens and know their opinions about important stances and decisions to be taken in the Parliament. It also enhances the MP's ability to answer questions of citizens regarding issues and legislations and clarify what is ambiguous, enhance the MP's ability to define the problems, challenges and priorities faced by citizens.

Fourth question: are there any statistically significant differences of MPs' attitudes towards the impact of social media on the parliamentary performance from the perspective of Members of the eighteenth Parliament according to the difference of qualification?

Statistical analysis results concluded that there are statistically significant differences in both of the impact of social media websites on the regulatory role of the MP (Member of Parliament) and impact of social media websites on the interaction and communication of MPs with citizens because of the difference of qualification. However, no statistically significant differences are shown by the analysis results in both of coverage of social media websites of topics needed by MP in the Parliament of Jordan and impact of social media websites on legislative role of the MP because of difference of qualification as statistically significant differences of the impact of social media websites on the regulatory between bachelor and PhD were for the benefit of PhD. However, statistically significant differences of the impact of social media websites on the interaction and communication of MPs with citizens between diploma and below and bachelor were for the benefit of bachelor. On the other hand, statistically significant differences between bachelor and all other levels (diploma, master, PhD) for the benefit of (diploma, master, PhD). The researcher states that this result indicates that there is a relation between the MPs' awareness of the impact of social media websites and the development of their educational experiences. Like Al-Mashaqba study (2017) most studies insisted that different aspects of technology must be included in addition to social media websites to get MPs qualified.

Second: recommendations:

Based on the results the study recommends the role of MPs to be enhanced in follow-up of different social media websites such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram for being important to involve the citizens in the political process, know their opinions and define their problems and priorities. It is also recommended to hold training workshops for MPs (Members of Parliament) about how to deal with social media websites and about the electronic media. Additionally, it is recommended to increase the interaction of MPs (Members of Parliament) with followers and commentators of the citizens on their own pages, and clarify what they do not know, keep up with events and official events on social media networks.

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